

Report on the implementation of traditional and novel effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of prioritized substances

Deliverable Report

D14.9

WP14-Biomarkers of Effect

Deadline: March, 2022

Upload by Coordinator: 08 June 2022

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1 Authors and acknowledgements

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2 Glossary

BDNF: brain-derived neurotrophic factor

DHEA: dehydroepiandrosterone

E2: estradiol

ELISA: enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

FSH: follicle stimulating hormone

FT3: Free triiodothyronine

FT4: Free thyroxine

KISS1: kisspeptin gene

Kiss54: Kisspeptin 54 protein

LH: luteinising hormone

SHBG: sex hormone-binding globulin

TSH: thyroid stimulating hormone

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3 Abstract/Summary

The proposed HBM4EU effort to assess human adverse health effects due to environmental chemicals exposure using biomarkers of effect, has continued with the implementation of these indicators, as described in D14.8. In the HBM4EU aligned studies, a broad panel of classical and novel biomarkers of effect (e.g. brain-derived neurotrophic function, kisspeptin, reproductive hormones, thyroid hormones, metabolic markers, oxidative stress markers, among others) has been implemented.

However, some proposed biomarkers have not been validated and implemented, such as leptin and adiponectin. These important cytokines play a key role in the proper development of metabolic and reproductive function. Additionally, the relationships between exposure and effect biomarkers data in the HBM4EU aligned studies have also not been reported. Therefore, the aims of this deliverable were to show: i) the quality control and quality analysis of leptin and adiponectin, as well as their measured concentrations in the aligned studies; ii) the physiological validation of kisspeptin (serum protein concentrations, kiss54, and whole blood DNA methylation of the *KISS1* gene), in a pilot study within the INMA-Granada cohort, to investigate its suitability as effect biomarker of the reproductive function prior to their application in HBM4EU aligned studies; and iii) the preliminary results of the exposure-effect analyses conducted in the Aligned studies. For this purpose, leptin and adiponectin protein levels were measured using different commercial enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA).

The new quality control procedure for leptin measurements showed that the chosen ELISA kit was a reproducible and confident analytical technique. Adiponectin was then measured in adolescent's serum samples from the aligned studies, including the FLEHS, PCB, BEA, and SLO CRP studies; as well as in children from the SLO CRP study. Leptin concentrations were also measured in adolescents from the FLEHS studies and in children from the SLO CRP studies. On the other hand, preliminary data with INMA-Granada blood and serum samples demonstrate the physiological feasibility of implementing new biomarkers of reproductive function, such as KISS, at different levels of biological organisation. The results showed that percentages of *KISS1* DNA methylation were inversely correlated with the serum concentrations of kiss54 protein, as well as with the serum concentrations of the selected reproductive hormones (FSH, estradiol, testosterone, SHBG). Moreover, levels of kiss54 were positively correlated with all reproductive hormones.

Thus, the pilot study with samples from INMA-Granada demonstrated the technical feasibility of implementing kisspeptin at different levels of biological organisation to assess the reproductive function in the HBM4EU aligned studies. Finally, when the kisspeptin effect biomarker (serum kiss54) data were analysed together with serum concentrations of reproductive hormones in the aligned studies, consistent results with the findings described in the pilot study were found, indicating that the novel effect biomarker KISS is a valuable marker of reproductive function useful for assessing possible alterations caused by environmental pollutants.

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4 Introduction

In this last deliverable, we report the implementation of traditional and novel effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of prioritised substances. For this purpose and continuing with the work done by WP14 we briefly remind the characteristics of a valid biomarker to detect chemically-induced adverse outcomes in animals and humans. Biomarkers should demonstrate the correlation with the response which is trying to predict as well as having an acceptable selectivity, specificity, adequate sensitivity and cover an appropriate measurement range (Baken et al. 2019, Mustieles et al., 2020, Rodríguez-Carrillo 2022, Steffensen et al 2020). The biology and performance of the biomarker are aligned with its use and they should have an acceptable magnitude of changes in response to the environmental compound. Moreover, analytical, and clinical validation should show that the biomarker is appropriated for its proposed use and a satisfactory intra- and inter-subject variability associated with the biomarker's baseline and response is necessary (Zare Jeddi et al. 2021a, b).

In this regard, a selection of classical (reproductive and thyroid hormones markers as well as some metabolic parameters) and novel (the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), and Kisspeptin (KISS54)) effect biomarkers was performed. Other classical biomarkers were also considered: the biomarker 8-hydroxy-2-deoxyguanosine (8OHdG) which may provide information on damage caused by elevated levels of oxidants (i.e., oxidative stress) and also on capacities of the studied biological system to respond to oxidative stress and/or the capacity of detoxification in general (Kozlowsha et al., 2022; Mustieles et al. 2022, Rodríguez-Carrillo et al 2022 a, b, Ventura et al., 2021

The selection of both classic and novel effect biomarkers (Deliverables D14.2, D14.3) was based on comprehensive literature searches conducted inside WP14, and together with toxicological and adverse outcome pathway (AOP) information collected in WP13 (Baken et al., Mustieles et al., 2020). These biomarkers were meant to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies and selected prospective European birth cohorts.

WP14 received serum, plasma, urine, and whole blood samples from different European birth cohorts (AD8.4 and D14.8). Effect biomarkers analyses for the first and second set of prioritised substances began during the global pandemic of COVID-19, with subsequent delays. By the end of October 2021, almost all classical and novel effect biomarkers were measured, except for adiponectin and leptin, which analyses will finish before mid-June.

Therefore, all cohorts (except NEB II) have been fully analysed, and data regarding the new effect biomarkers serum BDNF protein, and Kisspeptin 54 protein, as well as the classical effect biomarkers have been sent to the study owners as well as to the WP10 leader. In addition, serum BDNF protein, and Kisspeptin 54 protein levels from the PCB cohort (Slovakia) and the SLO CRP cohort (Slovenia), NEB II (Norway), the INAIRQ cohort (Hungary), and the NAC II cohort (Italy), have been evaluated and sent to their respective study owners. The remaining analysis of classical biomarkers are from samples of NEB II. This delay was due to problems in samples shipment from Norway biobank, however, samples are currently being processed and will be finished by the end of June 2022.

The OHdG in urine samples from the HBM4EU aligned studies were analysed in samples from SK and ESP. In the samples received, MU also assessed creatinine levels. All results were provided to the owners of the corresponding studies (SZU in SK and ISCIII in ESP).

INSERM has validated DNA methylation (*KISS1*) and histone modifications in the VITO samples (FLEHS cohort) and in a Spanish pilot Study (INMA cohort). However, the other Epigenetics

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biomarkers analysis in the remaining cohorts (NIPH and JSI) will not be finished by June, since INSERM partners could not receive human biological samples from the Aligned Studies due to long administrative process required to import the samples.

Thus, the status of the analyses in children and teenagers (Tables 1 and 2) and the preliminary results of adiponectin and leptin measurements are detailed in the following chapters.

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Table 1: Overview table analysis in children conducted under WP14

Implementation biomarkers of effect in children	MATRIX	Region	North	East		South	
		Study	NEB II - NIPH	PCB - SZU	INAIHQ - NPHI	SLO CRP - JSI	NAC II - EPIUD
		Country	NO	SK	HU	SL	IT
		N° samples	300	300	264	148	300
		Age (years)	6-11	10-12	8-11	7-10	6-8
Clinical effect biomarkers (TSH, T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, SHBG)	Serum		√1 Ongoing (UGR)	-	-	√ Done (UGR) (Plus leptin and adiponectin)	-
BDNF	serum		-	-	-	√ Done (UGR)	-
BDNF	Urine		√ Done (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)	-	√ Done (UGR)
Kisspeptin	Plasma		√ Done (UGR)	-	-	-	-
Targeted DNA methylation (BDNF)	Whole blood		√ Pending (INSERM)	-	-	√2 Pending (INSERM)	-
Histone modifications (ER, AR, TR)	Whole blood		√ Pending (INSERM)	-	-	√ Pending (INSERM)	-

“√” = parameter committed to be analysed, “-” = parameter not committed to be analysed.

1 NIPH: Only a subset of the clinical markers will be assessed, 7 of the 8 clinical parameters: T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, and SHBG (7*25 µL).

2 Extracted DNA will be sent for DNA methylation analysis instead of whole blood

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Untargeted DNA methylation	Whole blood		A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available children samples. Pending (INSERM)
Untargeted histone modifications	Whole blood		A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available children samples. Pending (INSERM)

Table 2. Overview table analysis in teenagers conducted under WP14

Implementation biomarkers of effect in <u>teenagers</u>	MATRIX	Region	North	East	South		West
		Study	NEBII - NIPH	PCB - SZU	SLO CRP - JSI	BEA - ISCIII	FLEHS IV - VITO
		Country	NO	SK	SL	ES	BE
		N samples	184	300	98	300	300
		Age (years)	12-14	15-16	12-15	14-16	14-15
Clinical effect biomarkers (LH, FSH, TT, E2, SHBG, glucose, insulin, TG, TC, HDL-C, LDL-C, leptin, adiponectin, TSH, T3, T4)	Serum		√ ³ Ongoing (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)
Kisspeptin	serum		√ ⁴ Done (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)	√ Done (UGR)
8-OHdG	Urine		-	√ Done (MU)		√ Done (MU)	
Targeted DNA methylation (Kisspeptin)	Whole blood		√ Pending (INSERM)	-	√ Pending (INSERM)	-	√ Pending (INSERM)

³ NIPH: Only a subset of the classical biomarkers will be assessed, both in children and teenagers, i.e. 7 of the classical parameters: T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, and SHBG (8*25 uL). As part of another study the other classical biomarkers were measured and these data will be shared. Classical biomarkers and BDNF will be measured in plasma instead of serum.

⁴ NIPH: Kisspeptin will be analysed in plasma.

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Implementation biomarkers of effect in <u>teenagers</u>	MATRIX	Region	North	East	South		West
		Study	NEBII - NIPH	PCB - SZU	SLO CRP - JSI	BEA - ISCIII	FLEHS IV - VITO
		Country	NO	SK	SL	ES	BE
		N samples	184	300	98	300	300
		Age (years)	12-14	15-16	12-15	14-16	14-15
Histone modifications (<i>ER, AR, PPARα, PPARγ, GR, TR</i>)	Whole blood		√ Pending (INSERM)	-	√ Pending (INSERM)	-	√ Pending (INSERM)
Untargeted DNA methylation	Whole blood		A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available teenager samples. Pending (INSERM)				
Untargeted histone modifications	Whole blood		A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available children samples. Pending (INSERM)				

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5 Methods

In section 4.6 of Deliverable 14.8, titled: "Adiponectin & Leptin: fine-tuning, precision and accuracy fine-tuning", the quality control and the pilot study for both metabolic biomarkers, is showed in detail. However, due to the COVID pandemic together with the Ukrainian War, the ENZO ELISAs kits (Human Leptin, ADI-900-028A) used for this quality control were no available. For this reason, a new company was chosen. The corresponding new quality control with INVITROGEN ELISA kit (Human leptin ELISA kit, KAC2281, Thermo Fisher Scientific) is shown below.

5.1 Quality control for Leptin (a classic effect biomarker)

UGR team has developed the appropriated methodology to measure the leptin levels, as metabolic marker, in human serum samples for their implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies.

Quality Control (QC) and Pilot Study: Leptin

According to the quality control designed, each serum sample was analysed in duplicate using two different plates. Initially, only one dilution was performed (1:100), being the condition proposed by the manufacturer. The initial volume to measure this metabolic marker was 5 µL of each sample tested in this pilot study.

Sample preparation

Each sample was assessed in duplicate at dilution 1:100 with a 500 µL as a final volume, as indicated below and in the Figure 1.

- Dilution (1:100): 5 µL of serum sample + 495 µL of Standard Diluent Buffer

Figure 1: Procedure followed to perform the assay

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Reagents preparation for ELISA kit procedure

- Wash Buffer (1x): Wash Buffer Concentrate (25x) should be diluted 25-fold with distilled water before using (50 ml of Wash Buffer Concentrate (25x) with 1250 mL of deionised water).
- Streptavidin-Peroxidase (SAV-HRP) (1x): Streptavidin-HRP (100x) should be diluted 100-fold with Streptavidin-Peroxidase (HRP) Diluent within 15 minutes of usage (120 µL of Streptavidin-HRP (100x) with 12 mL of Streptavidin-HRP Diluent).
- Leptin Standard Curve: The standard curve is prepared with seven points of calibration (Figure 2):

Stock solution (10000 pg/ml) = powder + 1.6 ml Standard Diluent Buffer (swirl or mix gently and allow to sit for 10 minutes to ensure complete reconstitution).

- Std. 1 (1000 pg/ml) = 100 µL Stock solution + 900 µL Standard Diluent Buffer
- Std. 2 (500 pg/ml) = 300 µL Std.1 + 300 µL Standard Diluent Buffer
- Std. 3 (250 pg/ml) = 300 µL Std.2 + 300 µL Standard Diluent Buffer
- Std. 4 (125 pg/ml) = 300 µL Std.3 + 300 µL Standard Diluent Buffer
- Std. 5 (62.5 pg/ml) = 300 µL Std.4 + 300 µL Standard Diluent Buffer
- Std. 6 (31.3 pg/ml) = 300 µL Std.5 + 300 µL Standard Diluent Buffer
- Std. 7 (15.6 pg/ml) = 300 µL Std.6 + 300 µL Standard Diluent Buffer

Zero Std. (0 pg/ml) o Blank = 300 uL Standard Diluent Buffer

Figure 2: Standard Curve preparation

Assembly of the leptin microplate

Standards, blank and samples are added in the wells according to the quality control design, which is briefly explained below: Rows 1 and 2 are designed for standards, while rows 3 to 12 are designed for analysed samples.

Specifically, diluted samples are loaded on rows 3 to 10 of plate 1 and their duplicates on plate 2, to calculate the inter-assay coefficient of variability (CV). To obtain the intra-assay CV, the duplicates of raw sample 11 are loaded into raw sample 12, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Quality control designed to measure leptin in serum samples

Leptin levels were measured by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using the Human leptin ELISA kit, KAC2281 (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific, Frederick, MD). Serum samples were selected from Belgium adolescent (n=78) belonging to the FLEHS Cohort (VITO). Samples were thawed, vortex-mixed, diluted (1:100) and analysed according to the manufacturer's instructions at the Centro de Investigación Biomédica (CIBM) of the University of Granada (Spain), as can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Quality control designed for serum leptin levels

ELISA kit procedure was carried out as describe below:

1. Add 100 μ L of Blank (Standard Diluent Buffer), standards and serum samples dilute at 1:100 in the appropriate wells.
2. Add 100 μ L of biotinylated anti-Hu leptin (Biotin Conjugate) solution into each well except the chromogen blanks (empty wells). Tap gently on the side of the plate to mix.
3. Cover plate with a plate cover and incubate for 2 hours at room temperature.

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4. Thoroughly aspirate or decant solution from wells and discard the liquid. Wash wells adding 400 μ L/well of Wash Buffer (1x). Repeat 3 more times for a total of 4 washes.
5. Add 100 μ L Streptavidin-HRP Working Solution to each well except the chromogen blanks.
6. Cover plate with the plate cover and incubate for 30 min at room temperature.
7. Thoroughly aspirate or decant solution from wells and discard the liquid. Wash wells adding 400 μ L/well of Wash Buffer (1x). Repeat 3 more times for a total of 4 washes.
8. Add 100 μ L of Stabilised Chromogen to each well. Incubate for 30 minutes at room temperature and in the dark.
9. Add 100 μ L of Stop Solution to each well. Tap side of plate gently to mix.
10. Read the absorbance of each well at 450 nm within 2 hours after adding the Stop Solution.

The aim of this Quality Control was to check that the new ELISA kit was suitable for leptin quantification. 78 serum samples from the FLESH-Cohort (VITO) have been used in this assay. The assay procedure was performed according to the manufacturer's protocol. Samples were evaluated in duplicate and the mean value was calculated to obtain the level of leptin present in each serum sample analysed. The results obtained indicate that the 1:100 dilution is a suitable dilution for measuring leptin levels in serum samples, as indicated in the manufacturer's protocol, since the optical density (450 nm) obtained for all selected samples was found to be within the linearity of the standard curve. LOD value is 3.5 pg/mL and LOQ value is 15.6 pg/mL.

The intra- and inter-assay coefficients of variability were 2.92% and 5.90%, respectively, both quality parameters within the manufacturer's guidelines, < 5% for intra-assay and < 15% for inter-assay. Figure 5 shows the distribution of leptin levels in the selected serum samples from the FLESH-Cohort (VITO). In summary, serum leptin levels ranged from 0.54 ng/mL to 41.73 ng/mL, and the mean and geometric mean were 9.87 and 5.80 ng/mL, respectively. The distribution of total serum leptin concentrations was as follows P25th = 2.48 ng/mL, P50th= 6.75 ng/mL and P75th= 14.78 ng/mL.

Figure 5: Distribution of leptin levels in the selected serum samples (n=78) from the FLESH-Cohort (VITO)

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6 Results

6.1 Adipokine markers in the HBM4EU aligned studies

Adiponectin and leptin were measured in serum samples of children and teenagers who took part in the Aligned Studies using the adiponectin ELISA kit (human) ALX-850-377 (ENZO Life Science, Farmingdale, NY), and leptin Human ELISA kit, KAC2281 (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific, Frederick, MD), respectively. Serum levels of adiponectin have been measured in teenagers from FLEHS (VITO, Belgium), PCB (SZU, Slovakia), BEA (ISCIII, Spain), and SLO CRP (JSI, Slovenia) studies; and in children from the SLO CRP study. Although leptin measurements are still ongoing, it has been already measured in teenagers from FLEHS and children from SLO CRP studies.

Analyses are expected to finish by mid-jun. A brief description on the new quality control conducted for leptin and the central dispersion and quality values of adiponectin and leptin already measured are detailed in the following sections.

6.1.1 FLEHS cohort (VITO-Belgium)

6.1.1.1 Adiponectin

Adiponectin concentrations were measured in 239 serum samples from Belgium teenagers (FLEHS cohort, VITO). Distribution concentrations are graphically summarised in **Figure 6**. Three assays were necessary to measure adiponectin in this study. Central dispersion values are available in Table 3. Mean (SD) serum adiponectin were 15.62 (5.20) $\mu\text{g/mL}$, showing 4.76 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ as minimum, and 38.21 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ as maximum. Total inter-coefficient of variation (mean of inter-CVs from the three independent assays) was 4.43%, thus deemed positive for optimal quality (Table 3). No incidents were reported.

Figure 6: Serum adiponectin levels ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) in an adolescent population: FLEHS cohort (Belgium)

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Table 3: Serum adiponectin levels (µg/mL) in an adolescent population: FLEHS cohort (Belgium)

	Summary (µg/ml)	Assay 1	Assay 2	Assay 3
Average	15.619	16.386	14.760	15.720
Median	14.902	15.644	14.330	14.651
Geometric median	15.564	15.725	14.001	14.702
SD	5.203	4.841	4.635	5.848
Max.	38.206	31.659	27.238	38.206
Min.	4.758	8.279	4.758	5.126
Pth25	11.725	13.284	11.432	11.202
Pth50	14.902	15.644	14.330	14.651
Pth75	18.588	18.645	17.260	19.255
CV-Inter (%) <15%	4.43	5.57	2.96	4.76
CV-Intra (%) <5%	3.55	3.99	3.73	2.92

6.1.1.2 Leptin

Serum leptin concentrations were measured in 239 adolescents of the FLEHS cohort. A total of three assays were performed. Distribution concentrations and dispersion measurements are available in Figure 7, and Table 4, respectively. Mean (SD) serum leptin was 10.69 (11.59) ng/mL, with a minimum and maximum values of 0.04 and 89.89 ng/mL, respectively. Total inter-coefficient of variation (mean of inter-CVs from the three independent assays) was 5.77%, deemed positive for optimal quality (Table 4). No incidents were reported.

Figure 7: Serum leptin levels (ng/mL) in an adolescent population: FLEHS cohort (Belgium)

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Table 4: Serum leptin levels (ng/mL) in an adolescent population: FLEHS cohort (Belgium)

	Summary (ng/ml)	Assay 1	Assay 2	Assay 3
Average	10.690	9.868	10.926	11.242
Median	7.245	6.748	7.848	6.501
Geometric median	7.501	5.797	6.536	5.032
SD	11.590	8.955	10.647	14.390
Max.	89.887	41.729	49.467	89.887
Min.	0.041	0.539	0.583	0.041
Pth25	2.362	2.480	2.732	2.000
Pth50	7.245	6.748	7.848	6.501
Pth75	14.955	14.775	14.764	15.449
CV-Inter (%) <15%	5.77	5.9	5.56	5.86
CV-Intra (%) <5%	2.96	2.92	2.79	3.18

6.1.2 PCB COHORT (SZU-Slovakia)

6.1.2.1 Adiponectin

UGR received 289 serum samples from PCB cohort which were immediately kept at -80°C. Four assays were needed to measure serum adiponectin levels. No incidences were found while performing the assays. Distribution of serum adiponectin concentrations (**Figure 8**) showed a mean (SD) value of 11.83 (4.65) µg/mL, minimum concentrations of 3.40 µg/mL and maximum concentrations of 27.59 µg/mL. Total inter-coefficient of variation (CV) was 4.98 %, indicating that adiponectin data followed an optimal quality (Table 5).

Figure 8: Serum adiponectin levels (µg/mL) in an adolescent population: PCB cohort (Slovakia)

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Table 5: Serum adiponectin levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in an adolescent population: PCB cohort (Slovakia)

	Summary ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$)	Assay 1	Assay 2	Assay 3	Assay 4
Average	12.658	13.701	12.767	11.378	12.982
Median	11.830	12.824	12.022	10.458	11.246
Geometric median	12.395	12.978	11.997	10.658	12.143
SD	4.653	4.656	4.555	4.110	5.007
Max.	27.587	26.373	27.587	26.294	25.714
Min.	3.395	6.769	4.647	3.395	5.949
Pth25	9.326	11.144	9.528	8.686	9.412
Pth50	11.830	12.824	12.022	10.458	11.246
Pth75	15.016	15.348	15.392	13.766	15.110
CV-Inter (%) <15%	4.98	4.76	4.41	5.56	5.17
CV-Intra (%) <5%	3.77	4.53	3.13	3.47	3.93

6.1.3 BEA cohort (ISCIII-Spain)

UGR received 295 serum samples from the BEA cohort. Four assays were needed to measure adiponectin concentrations in teenagers from this cohort. Distribution and central dispersion of measurements are showed in Figure 9 and Table 6, respectively. No incidences were found when performing these assays. Mean (SD), minimum and maximum concentrations of serum adiponectin 12.78 (5.04) $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, 2.08 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, 31.08 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively (Table 6). The total coefficient of variation (CV) was 4.76 %, indicating that adiponectin data are of optimal quality (Table 6).

Figure 9: Serum adiponectin levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in an adolescent population: BEA cohort (Spain)

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Table 6: Serum adiponectin levels (µg/mL) in an adolescent population: BEA cohort (Spain)

	Summary (µg/ml)	Assay 1	Assay 2	Assay 3	Assay 4
Average	13.470	12.896	14.114	13.521	13.265
Median	12.784	12.504	13.781	12.536	12.285
Geometric median	12.051	11.916	13.196	12.702	12.284
SD	5.037	4.786	5.075	4.984	5.268
Max.	31.080	23.827	27.091	28.768	31.080
Min.	2.080	2.080	4.354	6.714	5.235
Pth25	9.258	8.606	10.342	9.575	8.741
Pth50	12.784	12.504	13.781	12.536	12.285
Pth75	16.711	16.979	17.036	16.309	16.844
CV-Inter (%) <15%	4.76	3.96	3.37	5.93	5.77
CV-Intra (%) <5%	3.34	2.87	3.63	2.95	3.91

6.1.4 SLO CRP cohort (JSI-Slovenia)

6.1.4.1 Adiponectin (adolescents)

UGR reived 93 serum samples from teenagers of the SLO CRP cohort. Two assays were needed to perform the analysis. Figure 10 and Table 7 summarise the distribution and central dispersion of serum adiponectin. Mean (SD) adiponectin was 9.75 (2.95); minimum and maximum values were 4.23 µg/mL and 16.73 µg/mL, respectively. Serum adiponectin was measured without incidences. Mean inter-CV of the two independent assays were 7.31%, deemed positive for optimal quality.

Figure 10: Serum adiponectin levels (µg/mL) in an adolescent population: SLO CRP cohort (Slovenia)

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Table 7: Serum adiponectin levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in an adolescent population: SLO CRP cohort (Slovenia)

	Summary ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$)	Assay 1	Assay 2
Average	9.751	9.679	10.013
Median	9.169	9.169	9.647
Geometric median	9.299	9.249	9.484
SD	2.950	2.877	3.268
Max.	16.727	16.727	15.955
Min.	4.230	4.314	4.230
Pth25	8.021	8.055	7.472
Pth50	9.169	9.169	9.647
Pth75	11.727	11.260	11.989
CV-Inter (%) <15%	7.31	7.64	6.97
CV-Intra (%) <5%	3.08	3.34	2.81

6.1.4.2 Adiponectin (children)

UGR received 130 serum samples from children of the JSI cohort, which were kept at -80°C . Two assays were needed to measure serum adiponectin levels. No incidences were found while performing the assays. Children adiponectin concentrations showed a mean (SD) value of 12.02 (3.37) $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, with minimum and maximum concentrations of 5.22 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 23.38 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively. Distribution of adiponectin concentrations are graphically showed in Figure 11. Total inter-coefficient of variation (CV) was 6.48%, thus, data followed an optimal quality (Table 8).

Figure 11: Serum adiponectin levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in a children population: SLO CRP cohort (Slovenia)

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Table 8: Serum adiponectin levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in a children population: SLO CRP cohort (Slovenia)

	Summary ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$)	Assay 1	Assay 2
Average	12.015	13.137	11.165
Median	11.600	12.591	10.720
Geometric median	11.958	12.712	10.744
SD	3.372	3.399	3.114
Max.	23.379	23.379	18.531
Min.	5.221	6.269	5.221
Pth25	9.764	10.781	9.171
Pth50	11.600	12.591	10.720
Pth75	14.287	15.115	12.545
CV-Inter (%) <15%	6.48	7.09	5.86
CV-Intra (%) <5%	3.02	2.12	3.91

6.1.4.3 Leptin (Children)

Serum leptin was measured in 130 samples from children of the SLO CRP cohort in two independent analyses. No incidences were reported while conducting the assays. Mean (SD) concentration of leptin was 6.21 ng/mL with minimum and maximum values of 0.81 and 36.84 ng/mL, respectively (Table 9). Distribution of leptin concentrations in children is shown in Figure 12. Mean CV inter-assay was 5.74 %, thus leptin values were deemed positive for optimal quality (Table 9).

Figure 12: Serum leptin levels (ng/mL) in a children population: SLO CRP cohort (Slovenia)

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Table 9: Serum leptin levels (ng/mL) in a children population: SLO CRP cohort (Slovenia)

	Summary (ng/ml)	Assay 1	Assay 2
Average	6.214	6.026	6.456
Median	3.134	3.615	2.246
Geometric median	3.618	3.740	3.609
SD	7.241	6.456	8.190
Max.	36.839	34.676	36.839
Min.	0.807	0.807	0.938
P25	1.746	1.815	1.737
P50	3.134	3.615	2.246
P75	7.361	7.378	7.310
CV-Inter (%) <15%	5.74	6	5.48
CV-Intra (%) <5%	3.06	2.91	3.2

6.2 Physiological validation of kisspeptin biomarkers in the Spanish INMA-Granada cohort

To physiologically validate the effect biomarker kisspeptin before its implementations in the Aligned Studies, a pilot study in the INMA-Granada cohort was conducted. The INMA-Granada is part of the Spanish INMA birth cohort (Environment and Childhood) study, a multicentre project performed in different geographical areas of Spain (Guxens et al., 2012). During the last follow-up of the INMA-Granada cohort (2017-2019), a total of 151 adolescent males aged 15-17 years, living in the Granada province (Spain), were contacted and their parents gave their consent to participate in this study. From those participants, we had available whole blood samples of 131, and for 104 also serum samples. UGR team measured the protein levels of kisspeptin (kisspeptin 54, kiss54) in available serum samples and INSERM team measured *KISS1* DNA methylation at four CpGs from the Exon IV in available whole blood samples. Additionally, available information regarding the reproductive hormonal levels (FSH, LH, TT, DHEA, E2, and SHBG) of these teenagers was included. Therefore, we wanted to know as one of the aims: (i) the levels of *KISS1* DNA methylation in whole blood samples as well as kisspeptin levels in serum, and (ii) the correlation between kisspeptin serum concentrations, *KISS1* DNA methylation patterns, and serum hormonal levels.

Table 10 shows the central dispersion of serum kiss54 and *KISS1* DNA methylation percentages. Figure 13 shows the concentrations of *KISS1* DNA methylation, since serum kiss54 concentrations were showed in previous reports. Correlation analyses were conducted to ascertain the relationship between kiss54 protein, its DNA methylation levels, and their relationship with reproductive hormones in INMA-Granada adolescent males (Figure 14). Serum kiss54 concentrations showed median (interquartile range, IQR) of 2.65 (2.53-2.81) ng/mL, and median *KISS1* DNA methylation percentages ranged from showed 63.41 % to 87.69 %. Thus, CpG2 and CpG 1 were the less and most methylated CpGs, respectively.

Table 10: Kisspeptin effect biomarkers dispersion in adolescent males from INMA-Granada cohort

Effect Biomarkers		Serum kiss54 (ng/mL)	CpG1 (%)	CpG2 (%)	CpG3 (%)	CpG4 (%)	CpGt (%)
Percentiles	25	2.53	85.73	61.62	75.97	79.47	76.03
	50	2.65	87.69	63.41	77.54	82.19	77.28
	75	2.81	89.7	64.41	78.95	85.25	79.29

Figure 13: Kisspeptin effect biomarkers dispersion in adolescent males from INMA-Granada cohort

Spearman's correlation analyses showed that CpGs #1, 2, 3, 4, and total CpGs methylation percentages were positively and significantly correlated among them and negatively correlated with serum kiss54 levels. Since it is expected that the higher the methylation, the lower its protein levels, these correlations followed a biological meaning (**Figure 14**). Moreover, *KISS1* DNA methylation patterns were inversely correlated with serum reproductive hormones, and CpGs #1 and 2 were significantly correlated with DHEA, E2, and FSH. Finally, serum kiss54 was positively correlated with all hormones, showing significant levels of correlation with serum total testosterone and SHBG.

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Figure 14: Spearman's correlation analyses between kisspeptin (KISS1 DNA methylation and serum kiss54 levels) and reproductive hormonal concentrations among adolescent males

6.3 Epigenetic markers in the INMA-Granada cohort

Although *KISS1* DNA methylation was measured in all 131 whole blood samples from the INMA-Granada available, we wanted to know whether the presence of BPA may affects DNA methylation. In 83 out of 131 samples, urinary BPA concentrations were also available. BPA values in the 83 samples ranged from 0.43 to 48.18 $\mu\text{g/g crt}$ (micrograms per gram of creatinine). We extracted DNA, bisulfite converted and amplify the region of promoter of *KISS1* gene containing CpG1 to CpG4 (Figure. 15). PCR product was purified, quantity estimated, samples were validated via agarose gel loading and sent for pyrosequencing. Results of pyrosequencing in INMA cohort shows the level of DNA methylation in each CG has some variation in methylation levels [CG1=87.5+/-3.95, CG2=62.4+/-4.5, CG3=76.7+/-3.92, CG4=81.1+/-7.2) % of methylation]. 5 samples did not pass a quality control and these samples were omitted from the analysis (Figure 16).

chr1:204196498-204196718, GRCh38/hg38

Forward →

```
GGTGTGGAGGATGGAAGAGCCGGTAAGAAGGAGAAAGTCC
CGCCTCGGAGGGCTCGGGTGGGGCAGGAGGAGAGGCTGCCT
CCAGTCACAGAGCCCG1GAGGCAGAGGCCTCCCAAGGTGCCAT
GCTCTTCAGGAGGGTCTGAGGAGGAGGGAGGGGCG2GCAGA
GTGGGCCTGTGCTTGAGAGCG3TCACCCCG4GGCTTTATAAAAG
GGATGTGATCAGGGA ← Reverse
```

Figure 15: Promoter of *KISS1* (human), CGs (light green color), primers (red color). The resulting product was sequenced using sequencing primer (green color)

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Figure 16: Results of pyrosequencing are presented as %methylation

In order to reveal whether the presence of BPA affects DNA methylation, samples were divided into two groups: first group has BPA values below 5.3, named “low” group (n=42, range from 0.46 to 5.3, average value=2.8) and in the second group, named “high” group, BPA values ranged from 6.07 to 48.18, average value=14.01 (n=41). To assess differences in CpG between groups, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test was used. Findings showed that CpG2 has significantly higher methylation level in high BPA group compared to low group. A tendency towards increasing methylation percentage in CpG4 was also observed, although it did not reach the statistical significance (p=0.08), (Figure 17). Remaining CpGs did not showed significant differences.

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Figure 17: DNA methylation levels at CGs. High BPA group showed the increase in CG methylation. CG4 showed tendency to increase, however the value did not pass the statistical cut off ($p=0.8$).

To evaluate new effect biomarkers for BPA exposure, a genome-wide sequencing of histone H3K4me3 (Arnoult et al. 2012) (marks associated with gene transcription and located mainly at transcription start sites) was conducted in 10 samples of “low” group and 7 from “high” exposure group. To this end, paraformaldehyde crosslinked blood cells was sonicated, and chromatin immunoprecipitation was performed using antibody against H3K4me3 (Milipore) and protein A-coated dynabeads (Invitrogen). DNA was extracted and library was created using 5 ng of immunoprecipitated DNA. Samples were sequenced at single -end mode at the genomic platform. The sequencing reads were aligned to the reference hg38 human genome and quantitative analysis was performed.

The regions of the genome with altered histone H3K4me3 occupancies between low and high BPA groups were identified and functional annotation of the genes located within differential genes was performed. The analysis shows that 4297 genes are affected in high BPA group. Genes were annotated according to the functional analysis using GREAT program. It was found that the most significant groups combine the gene encoding proteins with important functions. For example, genes encoding factors relevant to histone H4 acetyltransferase activity and telomere-binding have altered H3K4me3 occupancy (Figure 18), suggesting possible alteration in the gene expression. The BPA exposure also significantly affects telomere binding proteins. Telomere proteins protect telomere from degradation and deregulation of telomere could lead to cellular senescence and genomic instability (Petti et al. 2015). We confirmed the effects of BPA on telomere proteins on human cell line exposed to BPA (data not shown).

These data show that exposure to BPA is associated with alterations in the methylation levels of *KISS1* gen, and alters many genes relevant to telomere function. Gene ontology analysis at the genome-wide level also shows that many pathways are affected by BPA exposure (Figure 18).

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GO Molecular Function

Figure 18: Gene ontology analysis at the genome-wide level

6.4 Epigenetic markers in the FLESH study from HBM4EU Aligned studies

A blood sample volume of 200 μL of blood from FLEHS cohort was obtained and divided in two tubes. From one tube DNA was extracted and then it was performed the copy number variation and DNA methylation analysis. The second tube was used for chromatin immunoprecipitation with H3K4me3. DNA was extracted and diluted to similar concentrations, qPCR was performed using unique copy RPLPO gene for the normalisation. Telomere length data is showed as telomere to unique copy gene ratio (T/S), which varies in human depending on tissue and cell types. The analysis of telomere length shows that the average T/S ratio in FLEHS is 1.049 ± 0.56 (Fig. 19, left). Interestingly, variations in T/S in FLEHS cohort were observed. Successively, a subset of ~ 107 samples were selected for DNA methylation and histone H3K4me3 analysis.

Figure 19: Telomere length analysis in FLEHS cohort. Samples were chosen to create three groups with different telomere length: low ($n=35$, $T/S=0.613 \pm 0.123$), medium ($n=36$, $T/S=0.93 \pm 0.09$) and high length groups ($n=36$, $T/S=1.55 \pm 0.515$).

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Telomere repeats show great variation in human population and are affected by toxic compounds. Thus, alterations in telomere length could be relevant to genetic instability.

To further proceed with analysis, we performed pyrosequencing of *KISS1* in all 298 samples. It should be highlighted that the average DNA methylation was similar to INMA cohort CpG1 (92.5±5.4), CpG2 (62.69±5.6), CpG3 (70.79±4.2) CpG4 (76.18±7.2) (Figure 20). Thus, it was observed similar perturbation on CpG2 in both cohorts suggesting that CpG 2 at *KISS1* may be vulnerable and could be associated with exposure to toxicants.

Figure 20: The DNA methylation in *KISS1* FLEHS cohort, DNA methylation at four different CpGs. Right image, the DNA methylation at low, medium, and high telomere groups. B) Quantitative analysis between groups showed the significant difference between low and high telomere groups at CpG2.

Next, to reveal the effects of pollutants on nuclear receptors, including steroid hormone receptors, a targeted analysis of histone H3K4me3 occupancy (marks associated with gene transcription) was performed in 107 samples. Samples were processed following the procedure of the INMA-Granada cohort by using chromatin immunoprecipitation protocol. Immunoprecipitated DNA was extracted and concentration of DNA was determined. Diluted samples were analysed in qPCR using specific primers for each target. Each target's value was corrected for background using RPLP0 region located far from transcription start site.

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Table 11: Targets were chosen for the analysis by CHIP-qPCR

Nuclear receptor	Encoded by	Natural Ligand
Estrogen receptor alfa	ESR1	Estradiol
Estrogen receptor beta	ESR2	Estradiol
Glucocorticoid receptor	NR3C1	Cortisol
Androgen receptor	AR	Testosterone
Thyroid hormone receptor alfa	THRA	Thyroid hormone
Thyroid hormone receptor beta	THRB	Thyroid hormone
Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor	PPARA	fatty acids, prostaglandins
Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor	PPARG	fatty acids, prostaglandins

This analysis showed that high telomere group have increased H3K4me3 occupancy at AR (encoding steroid hormone receptor) when compared with medium group. High telomere group has increased ESR1 occupancy when compared to low group (Fig.21). Low telomere group has lower H3K4me3 occupancies at ESR2 compared to medium group. High telomere group showed increased occupancy in H3K4me3 when it is compared to low group in THRB, PPARA, and OGG1 promoters. Finally, we analysed occupancy at SUV39H1 (encoding enzyme introducing histone H3K9me3 silencing marks) and TERT (encoding telomerase) which are not in table 11. Due to the importance of these factors for the telomere function, it was decided to analyse them. Thus, increased occupancy at TERT at high telomere group was observed, suggesting possible implication of TERT in telomere elongation of this group. The decrease in SUV39H1 promoter occupancy could be also potentially implicated in telomere shortening.

Brief summary of these two studies (INMA-Granada and FLESH cohort):

- It was observed alteration at CpG2 of KISS1 in two European cohorts suggesting that KISS1 promoter methylation analysis could be reliable effect biomarker due to chemicals exposure.
- It was observed alteration in regions in BPA relevant to telomere binding, suggesting that telomere function could be perturbed by exposure to estrogenic compound.
- It was detected that H3K4me3 histone occupancy in genes relevant to steroid hormones, detoxification and telomere functions were perturbed suggesting possible impact of pollutants on these functions.

All remaining samples from the FLESH cohort are finishing for the H3K4me3 analysis.

ChIP-qPCR data (1) - HISTONE MARK TARGETED : H3K4ME3

Figure 21: Targeted analysis of H3K4me3 at nuclear receptors and chromatin factors

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6.5 Preliminary results in the Aligned studies

Novel and classical effect biomarkers were measured in available serum samples using immunosorbent assays according to D14.7. Concentrations, central dispersion, and quality control values of all effect biomarkers are available in D14.7 and D14.8. Spearman's correlation tests were performed to assess the relationship between novel and classical effect biomarkers, including serum kisspeptin 54 protein levels as novel effect biomarker and FSH, TT, E2, SHBG, as classical reproductive effect biomarkers and thyroid hormones TSH, FT3, and FT4 as classical development effect biomarkers. These analyses are showed as heatmaps to enhance the reading (Fig. 22). Overall, serum kiss54 protein was positively correlated with reproductive and thyroid hormones, except for SHBG in FLEHS study (Fig.22.A) and TT in PCB, BEA, and SLO CRP (Fig. 22 B, C, D).

Figure 22: Spearman's correlation analyses between serum kiss54 concentrations, reproductive hormones, and thyroid hormones levels in teenagers of the Aligned studies. (A) FLEHS study, n=239; (B) PCB study n=289; (C) BEA study n=293; (D) SLO CRP study n=73.

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7 Conclusions

Although it is not yet possible to draw conclusions, the data indicate that the implementation of biomarkers of effect together with information on exposure levels in HBM studies can help epidemiological research to establish convincing causal relationships, and contribute to understand, resolve and answer some important policy questions. In this regard, for those aligned studies that have assessed exposure to specific compounds prioritised in HBM4EU, measured selected effect markers and have health effect information available, specific statistical analyses are being performed in relation to the established causal relationships exposure-health effects. The inclusion of biomarkers of effect may also help to understand the biological mechanisms through which exposure is related to adverse health effects.

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